
Research

Enhancing Customer Churn Prediction in Telecom: A Hybrid Strategy with Quartile Calculation and Random Forest

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Abstract: Predicting customer Churn is critical in all businesses to ensure the use of company's products by customers, and it has a significant impact on financial health and sustainability. However, predicting customer Churn in the telecommunication industry with high accuracy and interpretability is demanding. We propose an efficient Churn prediction model called Quartile Calculation - Random Forest (QC-RF) for telecom industry. First, the outliers are identified by QC algorithm and RF is applied for customer Churn prediction in our method. The proposed method has achieved at least 2% higher accuracy with a corresponding minimum of 3% higher F1-score compared with state-of-the-art algorithms on standard Telco-Customer-Churn dataset after balancing, SMOTE preprocessing, iteratively balanced. This work creates opportunities for both the development of better explainable models and a deeper understanding of Churn predictions in a more effective way and offers to improve the financial health and business sustainability of telecom companies.

Keywords: Churn prediction, Quartile Calculation, Random Forest, Classification

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Introduction

The rapid advancement of social media technologies has ushered in a new era for companies to engage with their customer base, both existing and new. The social media platforms have become powerful tools for businesses to connect with their audiences, get their feedback, listen, and adjust their products and services accordingly[1]. Simultaneously, the mobile communications industry has experienced a significant shift with an increasing number of customers actively changing their loyalty by moving their registered service from one competitor to another, exacerbating this dynamic of mobile telecom market saturation[2]. However, in the digital revolution, fierce competition has emerged among telecom service providers, who are striving to provide reliable communication and data coverage services, not only in urban areas but also in rural areas. This evolution has created an urgent need to meet the diverse needs of customers across the spectrum[3]. Telecommunication companies are turning to Machine learning (ML) to predict customer Churn, or

when a customer is likely to leave for a competitor. This is because it's more cost-effective to retain existing customers than acquire new ones[4]. These ML models can help identify customers at risk of Churning so that telecom companies can implement strategies to win them back. Customer Churn is a major financial burden[5]. This is because telecom companies lose not only the revenue from the Churned customer but also incur additional costs to acquire new customers. To minimize customers Churn, telecom companies are focusing on retaining existing customers.

Traditional methods of customer Churn prediction are complex due to the various factors. Researchers are turning to Artificial intelligence (AI) to address this problem. AI techniques like deviation prediction models and supervised Machine learning algorithms (MLA) can identify customers who are likely to Churn[6, 7]. These models are either static, based on customer characteristics, or dynamic[2], adapting to changing behaviors. Customer Churn prediction is essentially a classification problem[8], aiming to identify customers who will leave the service. The process of Churn prediction is complicated because of imbalanced datasets, where Churners are a smaller proportion. By analyzing a wide range of customer data, AI can predict Churn not only in telecom but also in other industries like webcasting[10], banking, shopping and etc.

This research endeavors to explore the dynamics of customer Churn, the development of predictive models, and the strategies employed by telecom companies to retain their customers. Understanding and mitigating customer Churn is essential for the sustainability and profitability of network service providers in the ever-changing telecommunications landscape. Solving the problem of highly imbalanced datasets is a relevant topic in the prediction of Churn[9]. Therefore, we balanced the classes of used dataset related to the Churn of telecommunication customers by applying the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE). Subsequently, we applied QC for detecting outliers in the dataset. Finally, we applied RF algorithm to solve the classification problem. This proposed approach achieved 90% accuracy, considering the execution time of the model.

The main objective of our proposed model is to improve the performance of the overall results and the robustness of the customer Churn prediction. This study makes the following main contributions:

- **Interpretability is improved by QC:** To solve the problem of ML interpretability, we will use outlier detection using QC algorithm. QC brings much needed transparency to improve ML interpretability.
- **Interpretable Model:** Shedding light into the value of feature engineering and accurate adept predictability for Churn prediction.
- **Elevated Churn Prediction:** We enhance the accuracy by using QC in Churn prediction as we integrate RF with it. The proposed method greatly improves the accuracy of prediction, and then, we trim the existing state-of-the-art models with 90% on Telco-Customer-Churn dataset.

The rest of the article is organized as follows. In Section 2, we review related work on the topic. Section 3 presents the methodology proposed in the research. Subsequently, in Section 4, we discuss the obtained experiment and analysis. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper and outlines directions for the future work.

Related work

In recent years, many techniques have been proposed by researchers such as Deep learning (DL) and ML to predict customer Churn in the telecommunication sector. A kernelized extreme ML technique was presented by Induja et al.[10], to categorize customer turnover trends in the telecom sector. After preprocessing the data using an Expectation Maximization (EM) clustering approach, a classifier model used to analyze customer turnover behavior based on four criteria: customer unhappiness, switching cost, service utilization, and customer status. They applied the Bat and KELM algorithms to measure the attributes to predict client attrition, the approach yielded an 83% area under the curve (AUC) score. K-nearest neighbor (KNN), RF, and XGBoost were utilized in study of[11] to forecast customer Churn; XGBoost obtained the accuracy of 79.8% and the highest AUC of 58.2%. RF and NB were employed by[12]. With an accuracy of 71.99%, their findings demonstrated that RF has provided better accuracy than NB, and they also discovered that the dataset was out of balance due to the experiments' lack of preprocessing. In their comparison of over 100 classifiers for

customer Churn prediction problems, Adhikary et al.[13] found that regularized RF outperformed all other classifiers by 67.20% in terms of AUC and that integrated RF using the bagging algorithm achieved the highest accuracy of 73.04%. To forecast customer attrition, Vijaya et al.[14] employed Particle swarm optimization (PSO) in conjunction with Feature Selection and Simulated Annealing (FSSA). They have found that PSO-FSSA performed best, with 94.08% accuracy and 96.06% F1 score in different dataset. The Rabbah et al.[15] study focused on forecasting customer Churn in the telecom industry. A multilayer stacking network with eight chosen models was created using ML, and it outperformed individual base models with an accuracy of 80.1%. This demonstrates how well the suggested strategy works to improve Churn prediction for telecom providers. Kumar et al.[8] compared MLAs to predict customer Churn in telecommunication industry. They found that these algorithms can be useful tools for customer retention. To address the imbalance in the dataset towards non-Churners, SMOTE and SMOTEENN sampling procedures were employed to create a more balanced training set. The results demonstrate the effectiveness of ML models in predicting client attrition. Furthermore, Ensemble learning (EL) models outperformed single-base learners, and it is anticipated that classifier performance would improve with a balanced training dataset. In the study of[16], the authors have employed ML algorithms to identify features associated with customer Churn. These studies often rely on clustering techniques to categorize features based on their importance in predicting Churn propensity. However, these approaches don't necessarily provide an accuracy measure for the Churn prediction model.

Several studies explore novel approaches for Churn prediction. One example is the three-stage method proposed in[23], They leverage DL techniques to convert data into images and extract features using Convolutional neural networks (CNNs), so their approach achieved an accuracy of 83.4%, outperforming other models in the literature. Another study by Lalwani et al.[17] used a Gravitational search algorithm (GSA) for dimensionality reduction and achieved 81.71% accuracy. However, one of the limitation of these studies is the lack of consideration for outlier detection and a dedicated classification algorithm. This paper introduces a proper approach by combining QC and RF algorithm along with appropriate feature engineering for predicting customer Churn in the telecommunication industry.

Research Methodology

The proposed methodology consists of three parts: Data preprocessing, classification due to the Churn prediction is a classification problem that in[18] employed RF algorithm to solve classification problem, and evaluation. Initially, we did the feature engineering to prepare data for the next step. In the second part we proposed QC for outlier detection to enhance the prediction result. In the third part we applied RF algorithm to classify the Churn (those customers are really want to leave or stop using of the exiting company services) and non-Churn (the opposite of Churn"customers are normally using company services "), as the case of Churn prediction is a binary classification problem[8]. The trained models undergo testing and evaluation while considering area under the ROC Curve (AUC) and other evaluation parameters (Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-Score).

A. The Dataset

The dataset consists of a substantial 7043 data points described in Tab. 1, each offering unique insights into customer behavior and characteristics, thereby forming the data source of our research. This term emphasizes that the "Churn" column identifies customers who have Churned within a recent period, typically the past month or quarter. Furthermore, the "Services" section furnishes valuable information about the spectrum of services individual customers have chosen, including telephone services, multiple lines, internet connectivity, online security, online backup, device protection, tech support, and access to streaming TV and movies. The "Customer account information" category contributes vital data about subscription duration, contract types, preferred payment methods, the preference for paperless billing, as well as details regarding monthly and total charges. Enriched with demographic details like gender, age, and family status, our dataset of 7043 data points provides a deeper understanding of customer behavior and

potential Churn triggers. This valuable information empowers us to conduct in-depth analyses and craft targeted retention strategies.

shows the main illustrated structure.

Fig. 1: Proposed model architecture

Tab. 1: Dataset Information.

	Num. Co	Columns	No. Instance	Data Type
	1	Customerid	7043	Object
	2	Gender	7043	Object
	3	Seniorcitizen	7043	Int64
	4	Partner	7043	Object
	5	Dependents	7043	Object
	6	Tenure	7043	Int64
B. Preprocessing	7	Phoneservice	7043	Object
	8	Multiplelines	7043	Object
	9	Internetservice	7043	Object
	10	Onlinesecurity	7043	Object
	11	Onlinebackup	7043	Object
	12	Deviceprotection	7043	Object
	13	Techsupport	7043	Object
	14	Streamingtv	7043	Object
	15	Streamingmovies	7043	Object
	16	Contract	7043	Object
	17	Paperlessbilling	7043	Object
	18	Paymentmethod	7043	Object
	19	Monthlycharges	7043	Float64
	20	Totalcharges	7043	Object
	21	Churn	7043	Object
		Total	287,943	

Feature engineering is a critical step in data preparation, particularly in addressing the challenges posed by imbalanced datasets. Balancing, an essential aspect of accurate classification, significantly influences the model's ability to effectively represent the classification performance. Accurately classifying instances from minority classes can be challenging due to their underrepresentation in training data[19]. To address this issue, we meticulously preprocessed the dataset, carefully separating features into two distinct categories: Numeric and categorical columns, based on their respective data types, this action facilitates appropriate transformations, enhances model performance, promotes interpretability, and enables effective handling of missing data. This step serves as a foundation for subsequent transformations. A prominent issue we encountered was the highly imbalanced nature of the dataset, as illustrated in Tab. 1. Our dataset consists of two classes: "Yes" with 1869 instance and "No" with 5174 instance. The "Yes" class represents instances experiencing Churn, while the "No" class represents those without Churn. An evident imbalance exists in the class distribution, necessitating corrective measures. To address this imbalance, we employed the SMOTE. This technique oversamples the minority class ("Yes") to achieve a more balanced distribution, as illustrated in Fig. 3 (unbalanced dataset before oversampling) and Fig. 2 (balanced dataset). Oversampling the "Yes" class mitigates the class imbalance issue, thereby facilitating improved model training and classification performance.

C. Feature Selection

Fig. 3: Distribution of Churn before balancing.

Fig. 2: Distribution of Churn after balancing.

Feature selection is a pivotal aspect in enhancing the overall performance of machine learning models[20], primarily contributing to the prevention of overfitting, optimization of computational efficiency, and improvement in generalization. In the context of a specific example, a dataset comprising 21 features was scrutinized, leading to the exclusion of the "gender" column. This decision was based on the understanding that the 'gender' feature held no significance or correlation with other features in the context of Churn prediction in our dataset.

D. Outlier Removal

Typically, algorithms for detecting outliers can be categorized into two primary groups: density-based approaches (e.g., LOF[21]) and distance-based methods (e.g., QC[22]). QC serves as a method employed in box plots. The range excluding

outliers is established as $[Q1-k (Q3-Q1), Q3+k (Q3-Q1)]$, where $Q1$ and $Q3$ represent the lower and upper quartiles, respectively, and k denotes a non-negative constant (typically chosen as 1.5). An observation is identified as an outlier according to QC if its value falls outside the specified non-outlier range. Our contribution lies in adapting this established method for our specific outlier detection task in Churn prediction domain. Algorithm 1 demonstrates the customized QC model used in this study.

Algorithm 1: Outlier Detection using Quartile Calculation

```

1: function detect_outliers (data, numeric_cols, and threshold=3):
2:   for col in numeric_cols:
3:     if not is_numeric (data [numeric_cols.index (col)]):
4:       remove_from_list (col, numeric_cols)
5:   data_clean ← copy (data)
6:   for col in numeric_cols:
7:     data_clean [numeric_cols.index (col)] ← zscore(data_clean[numeric_cols.index
(col)])
8:   outliers ← []
9:   for i in range (len (data_clean)):
10:    is_outlier ← False
11:    for col in numeric_cols:
12:      if abs (data_clean [i, numeric_cols.index (col)]) > threshold:
13:        is_outlier ← True
14:        outliers.append (i, outliers)
15:        break
16: function remove_from_list (item, list):
17:   if item in list:
18:     list.remove (item)
19:   return list
20: function delete_rows (data_clean, outlier_indices):
21:   return data_clean

```

Algorithm 1 Outline for proposed outlier detection, this algorithm was built to detect numeric outliers from a dataset. It uses z-scores and a cutoff point to mark records as outliers.

Key Steps:

Checking the Data Type: We can drop all the non numerical columns from the list of numerical columns here

- Data Cleaning and Z-Score Calculation
- Data is copied
- Z-scores are computed for each data point in the numerical columns

Outlier Identification:

An empty list is initialized to store outlier indices.

For each row:

- A flag is set to indicate an outlier.

For each numerical column:

- The absolute value of the Z-score is calculated.
- If the absolute Z-score exceeds the threshold (default 3), the outlier flag is set to True.
- If a data point is flagged as an outlier, the inner loop stops.
- If the outlier flag remains False after checking all columns, the data point is not considered an outlier for that specific threshold.

Outlier Removal: The `delete_rows` function is intended to remove outlier rows from the dataset.

F. Classification

Mainly, customer Churn prediction is a classification problem[8], that we need to classify which customers are Churn and which are not. There are many methods for binary classification: ML, DL, and etc.[23]. Classification methods are employed in Churn prediction to build models that can automatically identify customers at risk of Churning. These models leverage historical data to learn patterns and relationships, and they provide valuable insights for businesses to take proactive measures in retaining customers. In our work, we used a MLA which is RF to classify Churn with two parameters shown in below equations.

$$n_{estimators} = N = 100 \quad (1)$$

$$random_{state} = S = 42 \quad (2)$$

$n_{estimators}(N)$: The parameter representing the number of trees in the context of the RF algorithm.

$random_{state}(S)$: The parameter represents the seed for the random number generator in the context of the RF algorithm, so this value is flexible with model.

Experiment and Analysis

We used Python programming language in the Google Colab environment to implement the proposed method. Tab. 2 shows the experimental environment which shows more details about the tools that we used.

Tab. 2: Experimental environment.

Environment	Value
Operating system	Windows 11
CPU	Intel® Core™ i5-7200U CPU@ 2.50GHz
Memory	8 GB
Language	Python
Software development environment	Numpy, Pandas, Sklearn, Imblearn, etc.

The evaluation metrics encompass of accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-measure, which are defined in the below:

Accuracy: Correctly proportion classified samples to the total number of tested samples (3).

Precision: Correctly proportion classified positive samples to the total number of positive samples for a specific class (4).

Recall: It represents the correct proportion of identified positive samples to the total number of positive samples in the testing set for a specific class, as indicated by the equation (5).

F1-measure: The weighted average of recall and precision of each class or the entire classifier (6).

$$"Accuracy" = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (3)$$

$$"Precision" = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (4)$$

$$"Recall" = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (5)$$

$$"F1 - measure" = \frac{2*Precision*Recall}{Precision+Recall} \quad (6)$$

For a specific class, True Positive (TP) signifies the count of correctly identified positive samples, True Negative (TN) indicates the count of accurately recognized negative samples, False Positive (FP) represents the count of negative samples mistakenly classified as positive and False Negative (FN) signifies the count of positive samples erroneously categorized as negative.

A. Evaluation

In this subsection, we assess the performance of the proposed method using the dataset of "Telco-Customer-Churn" which is mentioned in Tab. 1 with details, with a focus on Churn prediction. To evaluate the proposed method effectively, we divided the dataset into two distinct parts: a training set comprising 75% of the data and a separate test set containing the remaining 25%. This division ensures that our model learns from a significant portion of the data while maintaining a distinct set aside for evaluation to assess its generalization capabilities. Fig. 4 visualizes the proposed QC-RF performance in the classification of Churn;

- **ROC Curve:** This curve shows the model's performance in distinguishing between positive cases (Churning customers) and negative cases (non-Churning customers). The AUC value is 0.97 indicates high performance.
- **Confusion Matrix:** This matrix shows the number of correctly and incorrectly predicted cases by the model. 847 out of 1021 Churning customers are correctly predicted (true positive), and 174 are incorrectly predicted as non-Churning customers (false negative). 45 out of 979 non-Churning customers are correctly predicted (true negative), and 1004 are incorrectly predicted as Churning customers (false positive).
- **Distribution of Predicted Probabilities:** This graph shows the predicted distribution of probabilities for all customers. Overall, the predicted probability is higher for Churning customers than for non-Churning customers.

In evaluating the effectiveness of our proposed QC+RF model for Churn prediction using the balanced dataset, we adopted a two-pronged approach. First, we aimed to establish a baseline understanding of the model's performance in isolation. Fig. 4 visualizes this initial assessment. The high AUC score signifies the model's strong ability to differentiate between Churning and non-Churning customers. Additionally, the confusion matrix reveals a minimal number of misclassified cases, further supporting the model's accuracy. Finally, the distinct probability distributions for Churn and non-Churn customers depicted in the figure provide a clear visual representation of the model's ability to separate the two classes. Secondly, to gauge the effectiveness of our QC-RF model relative to existing approaches, we conducted a comparative analysis. We specifically benchmarked our results against the latest advancements in the field, considered the state-of-the-art models for Churn prediction. Fig. 5 presents a detailed comparison, highlighting the superiority of our approach. As the figure illustrates, the QC-RF model exhibits significantly higher performance across all evaluation criteria, including precision, recall, accuracy, and F1-score. Notably, this superior performance is achieved with minimal training time, further emphasizing the efficiency of our proposed method. These results, in conjunction with the initial performance evaluation in Fig. 4, strongly support the effectiveness of the QC-RF model for Churn prediction within the "Telco-Customer-Churn" dataset.

Fig. 4: Churn classification performance.

B. Discussion

In this section, we comprehensively compare and discuss the obtained results and their implications for the Churn prediction domain. Our proposed QC-RF approach has demonstrated remarkable performance in Churn prediction on the "Telco-Customer-Churn" dataset. It is noteworthy that while previous methods have achieved notable results, our RF-QC approach outperforms them in all key metrics.

Fig. 5: Our work vs state-of-the-art in the datasets of Telco-customer-Churn

Fig. 5, Studies from the Some main ML methods and literatureBase on algorithms used in Churn prediction with the "Telco-Customer-Churn" dataset for Telecommunications, but many of these studies fail to reach peak performance to the best of our knowledge, we are filling this gap by proposing a new method based on combination of RF with QC for classification using a strong model. The idea behind that is to increase Churn prediction accuracy drastically.

To evaluate the performance of our proposed model, we also applied some famous ML techniques; Logistic regression (LR), Decision tree (DT), and Support vector machine (SVM), and we compared our result with the latest related work that mentioned in Fig. 5. The results of the machine learning models are evaluated based on the average of each evaluation parameter:

- LR: Accuracy (87%), Precision (83%), Recall (89%), F1-score (86%)
- DT: Accuracy (88%), Precision (83%), Recall (93%), F1-score (88%)
- SVM: Accuracy (81%), Precision (78%), Recall (82%), F1-score (82%)

Nikhil presented the results of our deep dive in to Churn prediction and compared them to some recent academic works. Fujo et al.[24] used a Deep Belief Propagation Artificial Neural Network (Deep-BP-ANN) model that achieved an impressive accuracy of 88%. While this emphasizes the high performance of Deep-BP-ANNs in the Churn prediction, it is inevitable to judge any model beyond its mere accuracy. A deeper sight on this work by Rabbah et al.[25] has been achieved with DeepInsight+StackNet and accuracy brought to 83%. Nevertheless, they have gone a step further in their study as other metrics such as precision, recall, and F1-score are also considered. It results in a balanced model performance: 83%, 81%, 83% and 82%.

Specifically, explaining with respect to a method we proposed - which uses the QC algorithm for outlier detection in the dataset and is followed by sophisticated feature engineering in the most ardent manner possible save a few useful heuristics to make the model classification rate confident in high performance changes, incorporating QC for this outlier detection makes it even more easily interpretable. QC will detect the outliers and experts are likely to analyze why the data points are far from their most common values, this way we can understand if they are important for the model prediction. Compares well to other works that have been studied, especially with regard the recall (89%). That indicates robust model to flag the false Churn cases as actual Churn cases. Although there was a little bump in recall for the DT algorithm nearly around (94%), this is expected because RF algorithm is also type of DT. But lower precision (83%) indicates that there might be some false positives, and further study would likely need if the model were to go into production. It was then the core of our project, as we tried to extract hidden predictive patterns from Churn signal using the RF algorithm and feature engineering, which is still used today to better inform around relevant information and not to fall into events that might dilute of becoming a real Churn signal. As a result, with 90% F1-score in all metrics which is high on balanced performance and simplicity of our model we have shown that it has great use for Churn prediction in telecommunication companies as reducing false negatives without blowing up positive ones is vital.

Conclusion

Customer Churn prediction is an inherent part of telecommunications customer retention and financial stability. To address this, we made an in-deep research about it. First we explore machine learning as a solution - specifically the RF algorithm - for Churn prediction. We further processed the data with QC algorithm and feature selection RF, which come to deals with outlier detection. The following performance metrics were prioritized in the model: Precision, Recall, Accuracy and F1-score with the aim of comprehensive evaluation. Our proposed QC+RF method showed marked improvement with 90% accuracy, outperforming recent academic benchmarks. This improved accuracy in turn means that the algorithm can get better and better at identifying customers who are likely to Churn, making it more effective for proactive retention strategies. Moreover, the unobtrusiveness of the approach facilitates its use by telecom companies for reducing customer Churn and in turn boosting their financial well-being.

For future work, other more optimized models should be investigated so that the efficiency of Churn prediction might be improved to a certain level and QC-RF may also have been evaluated on other Churn datasets. Moreover, the interpretability of the MLAs used should be addressed to make it more understandable how Churn predictions were made. Improving the resulting prediction systems will not only help succinctly predict Churn with greater accuracy and efficiency but also simplify to embed these prediction system to mainstream Churn management of telecommunication companies.

Code & data: Code and datasets used in this study are available upon request(rahimullah.rabih@gmail.com).

References

- [1] Y. Dai and T. Wang, "Prediction of customer engagement behaviour response to marketing posts based on machine learning," *Connection Science*, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 891-910, 2021.
- [2] N. Alboukaey, A. Joukhadar, and N. Ghneim, "Dynamic behavior based Churn prediction in mobile telecom," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 162, p. 113779, 2020.
- [3] A. Sridhar, G. Sharvani, A. Manjunatha Reddy, and K. Nagaraj, "Envisaging prominence of Indian telecom operators using an ensemble link based approach," *Indian Journal of Computer Science and Engineering (IJCSE)*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 297-310, 2020.
- [4] N. Lu, H. Lin, J. Lu, and G. Zhang, "A customer Churn prediction model in telecom industry using boosting," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 1659-1665, 2012.
- [5] V. Umayaparvathi and K. Iyakutti, "Applications of data mining techniques in telecom Churn prediction," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 42, no. 20, pp. 5-9, 2012.
- [6] Y. Beeharry and R. Tsokizep Fokone, "Hybrid approach using machine learning algorithms for customers' Churn prediction in the telecommunications industry," *Concurrency and Computation: Practice and Experience*, vol. 34, no. 4, p. e6627, 2022.
- [7] M. U. Tariq, M. Babar, M. Poulin, and A. S. Khattak, "Distributed model for customer Churn prediction using convolutional neural network," *Journal of Modelling in Management*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 853-863, 2022.
- [8] S. Kumar and D. Logofatu, "Comparative Study on Customer Churn Prediction by Using Machine Learning Techniques," in *Asian Conference on Intelligent Information and Database Systems, 2023*: Springer, pp. 339-351.
- [9] J. B. Brito *et al.*, "A framework to improve Churn prediction performance in retail banking," *Financial Innovation*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 17, 2024.
- [10] S. Induja and D. Eswaramurthy, "Customers Churn prediction and attribute selection in telecom industry using kernelized extreme learning machine and bat algorithms," *International Journal of Science and Research*, vol. 5, no. 12, pp. 258-565, 2016.
- [11] J. Pamina, B. Raja, S. SathyaBama, M. Sruthi, and A. VJ, "An effective classifier for predicting Churn in telecommunication," *Jour of Adv Research in Dynamical & Control Systems*, vol. 11, 2019.
- [12] M. A. Lejeune, "Measuring the impact of data mining on Churn management," *Internet Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 375-387, 2001.
- [13] D. D. Adhikary and D. Gupta, "Applying over 100 classifiers for Churn prediction in telecom companies," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 80, no. 28-29, pp. 35123-35144, 2021.
- [14] J. Vijaya and E. Sivasankar, "An efficient system for customer Churn prediction through particle swarm optimization based feature selection model with simulated annealing," *Cluster Computing*, vol. 22, pp. 10757-10768, 2019.
- [15] J. Rabbah, M. Ridouani, and L. Hassouni, "A new telecom Churn prediction model based on multi-layer stacking architecture," in *International Conference on Networking, Intelligent Systems and Security, 2022*: Springer, pp. 35-44.

- [16] Y. Liu, J. Fan, J. Zhang, X. Yin, and Z. Song, "Research on telecom customer Churn prediction based on ensemble learning," *Journal of Intelligent Information Systems*, vol. 60, no. 3, pp. 759-775, 2023.
- [17] P. Lalwani, M. K. Mishra, J. S. Chadha, and P. Sethi, "Customer Churn prediction system: a machine learning approach," *Computing*, pp. 1-24, 2022.
- [18] S. K. Wagh, A. A. Andhale, K. S. Wagh, J. R. Pansare, S. P. Ambadekar, and S. Gawande, "Customer Churn prediction in telecom sector using machine learning techniques," *Results in Control and Optimization*, vol. 14, p. 100342, 2024.
- [19] V. S. Spelmen and R. Porkodi, "A review on handling imbalanced data," in *2018 international conference on current trends towards converging technologies (ICCTCT)*, 2018: IEEE, pp. 1-11.
- [20] M. A. Hall, "Correlation-based feature selection for machine learning," The University of Waikato, 1999.
- [21] M. M. Breunig, H.-P. Kriegel, R. T. Ng, and J. Sander, "LOF: identifying density-based local outliers," in *Proceedings of the 2000 ACM SIGMOD international conference on Management of data, USA, 2000*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 93-104.
- [22] W. P. Zijlstra, L. A. Van Der Ark, and K. Sijtsma, "Outlier detection in test and questionnaire data," *Multivariate Behavioral Research*, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 531-555, 2007.
- [23] M. Makhtar, S. Nafis, M. Mohamed, M. Awang, M. Rahman, and M. Deris, "Churn classification model for local telecommunication company based on rough set theory," *Journal of Fundamental and Applied Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 6S, pp. 854-868, 2017.
- [24] S. W. Fujo, S. Subramanian, and M. A. Khder, "Customer Churn prediction in telecommunication industry using deep learning," *Information Sciences Letters*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 24, 2022.
- [25] J. Rabbah, M. Ridouani, and L. Hassouni, "New Approach to Telecom Churn Prediction Based on Transformers," in *The International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Computer Vision*, 2023: Springer, pp. 565-574.

